

Integrating topographic features into point cloud processing for terrain modeling

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Abstract—Terrain plays a dominant role in shaping surface processes. Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) are widely used for representing terrain surfaces. With advancements in UAV photogrammetry, high-resolution point clouds are widely used for terrain modeling. However, challenges arise in flat areas due to densely distributed point clouds, and in complex terrains where occlusions and filtering create gaps, affecting terrain modeling accuracy. Considering topographic features are critical for terrain modeling, this study integrates topographic feature elements and topographic derivatives into point cloud simplification and gap restoration for efficient and accurate terrain modeling. This study first extracts topographic features directly from points clouds. Second, the extracted topographic derivatives are used to simplify point clouds, i.e., extracting global control points and local terrain feature points. Third, the extracted topographic feature lines are incorporated into patch matching methods for point cloud gap restoration. The topographic feature-embedded patch matching method enhances its terrain similarity mining capability for more accurate restoration. The experiments results demonstrate that the topographic feature-embedded point cloud simplification and restoration methods improve the accuracy of terrain modeling. This work endeavors to incorporate topographic features into point cloud processing for terrain modeling and can benefit future research related to terrain modelling.

I. INTRODUCTION

Terrain is the dominant factor that constrains surface processes and phenomena on the Earth's surface system, exerting significant influences on geomorphology, climate conditions, hydrological processes [1]. The most commonly used terrain representation model, Digital Elevation Model (DEM), digitizes the surface morphology and contains rich terrain information necessary for geoscientific application analysis. With the development of remote sensing, Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) can rapidly and efficiently acquire massive and high-density point clouds using Structure-from-Motion and LiDAR techniques. These point cloud data are critical data sources for fine terrain modeling and analysis. However, there are many problems when using the acquired point

cloud data directly for terrain modeling. Specifically, in gently sloping areas, massive and dense point cloud data bring huge pressure on storage, analysis, visualization, and subsequent modeling and analysis. Therefore, point cloud data need to be simplified to reduce the data volume while retaining terrain feature points, aiming to accurately describe the surface morphology with fewer points, improving the efficiency of terrain modeling while keeping model accuracy. In complex areas, due to factors such as vegetation and building occlusion and filtering operations, the acquired point cloud data often have gaps of missing data. Traditional interpolation algorithms only focus on elevation information around gaps during the terrain modeling, ignoring the control role of topographic features on surface morphology representations, leading to less accurate modeling results in gap areas, particular in topographic features.

The morphological characteristics of the Earth's surface are controlled by topographic features, including topographic feature elements that play a controlling role in the spatial distribution of surface morphology, and topographic derivatives that can be used to effectively study and express landform morphological features. Currently, topographic features have been widely used in grid DEM-based terrain modelling and analysis [2-3]. Point cloud data can more finely describe surface morphology, and topographic features should also be fully considered during point cloud processing for further fine terrain modeling. However, currently point cloud processing methods, including point cloud simplification and gap restoration methods lack consideration of topographic features, which reduces the accuracy of point cloud processing and subsequent terrain modeling. Therefore, based on high-precision terrain point cloud data, this study incorporates topographic features in point cloud simplification and gap restoration for following accurate terrain modeling.

II. TOPOGRAPHIC FEATURE-EMBED POINT CLOUD PROCESSING METHOD

A. *Extractions of topographic features from point clouds*

Topographic feature elements refer primarily to point, line, or surface elements that have a controlling role in the spatial distribution characteristics of terrain surfaces. From the perspective of points, terrain feature points that have a controlling effect on the terrain are first selected, and then these points are topologically connected according to topographic feature morphologies to form topographic feature lines, with the areas enclosed by these lines forming topographic feature areas. Details for extracting topographic features from point clouds are shown in [4].

Topographic derivatives derived from surfaces can effectively study and express landform morphological features, such as slope, curvature, etc. These terrain factors of a target point can be directly calculated from the quadratic surface, fitted using the target point and its neighboring points, based on the formulas of the terrain factors [5].

B. *Integrating topographic factors into point cloud simplification (TFPCS)*

The extracted topographic derivatives are incorporated into point cloud simplification, which includes extracting globally controlling terrain points (Fig. 1(b)) and local terrain feature points (Fig. 1(c)).

1) *Extraction of global terrain feature points*

Global terrain feature points, including peak, saddle points, as well as points on ridge lines, mountain crests, and steep slope lines, are mainly distributed at terrain abrupt changes. These points can control the basic skeleton of the terrain. The profile curvature, which is the curvature along the direction of maximum slope direction, can effectively describe the characteristics of terrain abrupt changes, which therefore is used to efficiently extract global terrain feature points. Specifically, Jenks natural breaks method is used divided raw point clouds into two sets based on their profile curvature values, then uniformly sampling the point set with higher curvature values using a user-defined simplification rate to obtain global terrain feature points.

2) *Extraction of local terrain feature points*

Aside from global feature points, local terrain points are extracted to enrich terrain information, ensure the uniform distribution of final simplified points, and facilitate subsequent terrain modeling. Specifically, multiple terrain factors including slope, terrain relief, and total curvature accumulation are used to construct local terrain information indicators by weighted summation based on the CRITIC method [6], which not only considers the fluctuation degree of each factor but also considers the correlation between factors. These topographic derivatives reflect the characteristics of surface inclination, terrain relief, and material flow, respectively, ensuring the extracted local terrain points can represent local terrains.

Then, a grid simplification strategy is conducted to simplify point clouds. Specifically, point clouds in the sample area are divided into rectangular grids with a user-defined grid size, forming different sub-regions. In each sub-region, while retaining the global terrain feature points, the remaining points are simplified based on the constructed local terrain information indicator. The principle is that the larger the local terrain information value of a point, the higher the probability of retaining that point and the lower the probability of simplification. This principle is implemented through a roulette wheel selection method (Fig. 1(c)). The number of simplified points retained for each grid is based on the number of points in the grid and the average local point information indicator value of the grid.

The extracted local terrain feature points within the local grid can enrich local terrain details and information, increase the uniformity of simplified point distribution, and ensure the accuracy of subsequent terrain modeling. Finally, combining the extracted global terrain points with local terrain points yields the final simplified points (Fig. 1(d)).

Figure 1. (a) Framework of the proposed TFPM method. (b), (c), (d) are extracted global, loba and final simplified points, respectively. (e) The roulette wheel selection method.

C. Integrating topographic features and patch matching into point cloud restoration (TFPM)

The TFPM method first involves extracting boundary points of gap areas, and then repairing topographic feature lines within the gap areas, and finally applying the feature-embedded patch matching method to search other parts of the point cloud for patches resembling the gaps, and the identified patches are used as templates to restore the point cloud.

Figure 2. (a-d) Framework of the TFPM method. (g) Target patch. (h) Source patches. (i-n) Topographic feature line restoration and patch matching process. (o) Topographic feature lines.

1) Patch generation

After identifying the boundary points of a gap according to [7], a gap and its adjacent points constitute a target patch, which includes points within a buffer area of 3 times the average point distance (APD) from the gap's smallest outer rectangle (Fig 2. (g), $d=3 \times APD$). The source patch (Fig 2 (h)) is generated based on its corresponding target patch. Multi-scale matching strategy is adopted by generating multiple source patches of different sizes for each target patch to be repaired, i.e., source patch sizes are 1, 1.5, and 2 times the length of the corresponding target patch's longest side, denoted as 'size' in Fig. 2 (h) and 'h' in Fig. 2 (g).

2) Topographic feature line restoration

Before patch matching for point cloud restoration, it is necessary to restore the topographic feature lines that are possible to pass through the gap area.

First, use the DBSCAN algorithm to cluster topographic feature points within the target patch into multiple point sets. Next, fit the X and Y coordinates of each point set into straight lines. If the fitted lines intersect within the gap or are approximately parallel with a distance less than $3 \times APD$, they are matched and combined into candidate point pairs for terrain feature point repair. In complex environments, if a feature point set may match multiple other sets, the matched point sets with similar elevation values are selected. Then, fit the X and Y coordinates of each candidate pair into a 2D curve and sample points at APD intervals to interpolate X and Y coordinates. Finally, fit the X and Z coordinates of each pair into a quadratic curve to determine Z coordinates. The interpolated X, Y, and Z coordinates form the restored terrain feature points.

3) Patch matching for gap restoration

After restoring terrain features in gap areas, a topographic feature-embedded patch matching algorithm is used to explore global terrain similarity. The process involves three key steps: (1) Segmentation: Gap and target patches are divided into smaller subregions using fitted curves, with recovered topographic feature lines serving as boundaries. (2) Patch Matching: Each segmented target patch is matched with the most similar source patch from multiscale source patches, involving translation and rotation to align their geometric structures and improve similarity. (3) Gap Restoration: The source patch with the highest similarity, determined by the average elevation difference, is used to restore the gap, ensuring that only points within the gap range are retained. This method effectively repairs gap areas and enhances terrain continuity.

III. RESULTS

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Figure 3. (a), (d), and (g) are point clouds. (e) and (h) have human-removed gaps, located at topographic features. (c), (f) and (i) are rendered DEM maps.

Sample Areas 1-3 are point cloud data are acquired using the drone Structure-from-Motion techniques in the Loess Plateau, China, where Areas 1 and 2 are typical terraced areas, and Area 3 is sloped areas (Fig. 3). These point cloud are used to validate the proposed TFPCS and TFPM point cloud processing methods.

A. Point cloud simplification and terrain modeling

Figure 4. RMSE values of the grid-DEM modeling results using TFPCS, curvature, and random simplification methods under different simplification rates and grid sizes.

The proposed TFPCS is compared with the improved curvature and random simplification methods using the same grid simplification strategy as the TFPCS method. Fig. 4 shows the RMSE values of grid-DEM generated by different point simplification methods under grid sizes of 1 to 5 m with simplification rates of 90%, 95%, and 99%. Compared with the other models, the TFPCS method achieved smaller RMSE values overall in sample Areas 1 and 3. At a reduction ratio of 99%, compared to the best-performing comparative method, the TFPCS algorithm reduced the RMSE averages by 5% and 10%, respectively.

B. Point cloud restoration and terrain modeling

The proposed TFPM method is compared with the tradition patch matching method (PM), IDW interpolation method, quadratic surface fitting method (QSF). Fig. 5 shows the RMSE values of the generated grid-DEMs using the restored point cloud data in Area 2 and Area 3. The TFPM method has the lowest RMSE values in the generated grid-DEM in terraced fields and hillslope areas, with average RMSE reductions of 58% and 26%, respectively.

IV. CONCLUSION

This study incorporates topographic derivatives and topographic feature lines into the point cloud simplification and restoration processes, respectively. Comparison experiments showed the topographic feature-embedded point cloud processing

methods achieved higher terrain modelling accuracies, indicating the important role of topographic features in point cloud processing and subsequent terrain modelling. Further research is focused on integrating terrain features into other point cloud processing methods for terrain modeling, while also optimizing algorithm design to ensure that more information is incorporated during processing without significantly compromising the algorithm's efficiency.

Figure 5. The RMSE values of grid-DEM constructed using restored point cloud data in Area 2 and Area 3.

V. REFERENCE

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